

Spectrophotometric Determination of Some Metal Ions with Ortho Amino Phenol

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Manuscript received 5 May 1981, revised 28 January 1982, accepted 28 September 1982

The catalytic activity of Fe(III), Cu(II), Ru(III), Mo(VI), W(VI), Os(VIII) or Ir(III) in the oxidation of orthoaminophenol (OAP) by hydrogen peroxide to coloured 2-aminophenoxazin-3-one or 2-hydroxyphenoxazin-3-one has been utilised for the determination of these metal ions. In the case of Au(III), Cr(VI) and V(V), the metal ions themselves oxidize OAP to the same oxidation product even in the absence of H_2O_2 .

ORTHOAMINOPHENOL (OAP) forms complexes of varying stability with a variety of metal ions¹.

We have developed a precise and accurate spectrophotometric method for the determination of Fe(III), Cu(II), Ru(III), Os(VIII) or Ir(III) basing on the catalytic effect of these ions in the oxidation of OAP by H_2O_2 . In the case of Au(III), Cr(VI) and V(V), the metal ions themselves oxidise OAP to the same oxidation product even in the absence of H_2O_2 . Kinetic determination of Mo(VI)², W(VI)³ and Cr(VI)⁴ basing on the oxidation of OAP by H_2O_2 at pH 5.6-5.8 has been reported in literature but the methods are not precise and accurate. We have applied the spectrophotometric method for the determination of these ions also, the results of which are much more precise and accurate than in the kinetic method.

Experimental

Apparatus: Spectral and absorbance measurements were made with a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer, using 1 cm glass cells. Elico model LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Reagents: Methanolic solution of OAP (0.1%) was always freshly prepared. Hydrogen peroxide solution was prepared from 30% H_2O_2 and standardised by permanganate titration. Fe(III) solution was prepared from ferric ammonium sulphate (BDH, AR) in 1 N H_2SO_4 and standardised by permanganate titration after reduction. Copper(II) solution was prepared from copper sulphate (BDH, AR) in distilled water containing a few drops of acetic acid and standardised iodometrically. Ruthenium(III) solution was prepared from ruthenium trichloride (Johnson Matthey) in 1 M H_2SO_4 and standardised cerimetrically⁴. Mo(VI) solution was prepared from ammonium molybdate (AR) in water and standardised gravimetrically using 8-hydroxyquinoline. W(VI) solution was prepared from sodium tungstate (BDH, AR) in water.

Os(VIII) solution was prepared from osmium tetroxide (Johnson Matthey) in 0.5 M NaOH and standardised iodometrically⁵. Ir(III) solution was prepared from sodium hexachloroiridate(IV) (Johnson Matthey) using Poulsen procedure⁶ and standardised by permanganate titration⁷. Gold(III) solution was prepared from chloroauric acid (Johnson Matthey) in distilled water and standardised iodometrically. Chromium(VI) solution was prepared from potassium dichromate (BDH, AR) in distilled water. Vanadium(V) solution was prepared from ammonium metavanadate (Rea-Chem, USSR) in distilled water and standardised with iron(II) solution. Buffer solutions of pH 2.5-3.5 were prepared from potassium acid phthalate and hydrochloric acid solutions⁸. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade chemicals.

Procedure: 15 ml of buffer solution (if an organic solvent was used instead of buffer, HCl was added to maintain the desired pH), OAP and H_2O_2 were successively placed in a 25 ml volumetric flask. A 1.0-4.0 ml portion of the sample solution containing metal ion [Fe(III), Cu(II), Ru(III), Mo(VI), Os(VIII), W(VI) or Ir(III)] and requisite volume of distilled water were placed so as to make the total volume 25 ml. The absorbance was measured at λ_{max} (cf. Table 1) after maximum colour development against the reagent blank prepared under similar conditions. The metal ion concentration of the sample solution was deduced from the standard calibration curve.

In the case of Au(III), Cr(VI) and V(V) the same procedure may be adopted omitting the addition of H_2O_2 .

The experimental conditions needed for the determination of each metal ion are shown in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It is well known that OAP undergoes oxidative dimerisation by oxidant⁹ or simply by autoxida-

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DETERMINATION OF METAL IONS

Metal ion	λ_{max} under established expt. conditions nm	Buffer	pH Organic solvent (<i>i</i> -PrOH)	OAP solution 0.1% ml	H ₂ O ₂ solution 0.275 <i>N</i> ml	Time for maximum colour development hr	Stability of the colour hr
Fe(III)	400*-410		2.6-2.8	1	1	1.5	1
Cu(II)	410-420*-430		4.2-4.4	1	1	2.5	2
Ru(III)	400*-410		3.0-3.2	1	2	3.5	1.5
Mo(VI)	410-420*	3.0-3.2		1	1	4.5	1.75
	420-430*		3.0-3.2	1	1	3.75	0.75
W(VI)	410-420*	3.0-3.2		1	1	3.5	1
	420-430*		3.0-3.2	1	1	4	1
Os(VIII)	400-420*	3.0-3.2		1	1	4.5	1
Ir(III)	400-410*		1.30-1.5	1.5	1	3	1
Au(III)	410-420*	3.0-3.2		1	—	0.5	4.5
Cr(VI)	430*-450	3.0-3.2		1	—	0.5	22.5
V(V)	410-420*	3.0-3.2		1	—	0.75	30

* Wave length chosen for absorbance measurements.

TABLE 2—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC ESTIMATION OF METAL IONS

Metal ion	Beer's law limits $\mu\text{g}/25$ ml	Optimum photometric range $\mu\text{g}/25$ ml	Molar extinction coefficient at absorbance maxima $\text{l mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Relative mean error (%)	*Relative standard deviation (%)	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/0.01$ absorbance unit Proposed method	Reported methods
Fe(III)	0.0463-0.232	0.05-0.22	3.79×10^4	1.6	0.8	0.00015	0.045 ¹¹ 0.12 ¹²
Cu(II)	0.255-0.636	0.262-0.62	1.06×10^4	1.47	0.53	0.0006	0.26 ¹³ 0.018 ¹⁴
Ru(III)	1.35-2.7	1.4-2.5	3.33×10^4	1.38	0.53	0.008	0.19 ¹⁵ 0.15 ¹⁶
Mo(VI) (in buffer)	5.4-32.6	5.5-30	2.21×10^4	1.9	0.3	0.043	0.12 ¹⁷
(in 60% <i>i</i> -PrOH)	1.1-5.4	1.2-5.3	2.21×10^4	2.0	0.3	0.0043	0.038 ¹⁸
W(VI) (in buffer)	44.6-111.5	45-110	1.48×10^4	1.4	0.3	0.124	0.124 ¹⁹ 0.09 ²⁰
(in 60% <i>i</i> -PrOH)	55.7-83.6	56-82	3.31×10^4	2.0	0.3	0.06	
Os(VIII)	0.49-1.2	0.5-1.2	6.81×10^4	0.35	0.3	0.0028	0.07 ²¹ 0.328 ²⁰
Ir(III)	0.063-0.31	0.095-0.3	6.17×10^4	1.3	0.53	0.00081	0.21 ²¹
Au(III)	26-259	33-258	9.9×10^3	0.77	0.3	0.199	0.66 ²² 0.4 ²³
Cr(VI)	7.1-70.7	7-69	1.18×10^4	0.6	0.3	0.044	0.15 ²⁴
V(V)	17.4-261	25-260	3.51×10^3	0.4	0.3	0.145	0.27 ²⁵

* Each result is an average of eight separate determinations.

tion²⁰ leading to the formation of coloured 2-aminophenoxazin-3-one or 2-hydroxyphenoxazin-3-one. The reaction is pH sensitive (steady and slow up to pH 3.5 ; unpredictable and fast above pH 4.5). The optimum conditions were established basing on the development of maximum colour and its stability through variation of parameters such as pH (low pH preferred, even though more time was required, because of precision, accuracy and sensitivity), solvent (water, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, isopropyl alcohol, tertiary butyl alcohol or ethylene glycol) reagent concentration and sequence of addition.

Fe(III), Cu(II), Ru(III), Mo(VI), W(VI), Os(VIII) and Ir(III) catalyse the oxidation of OAP by H₂O₂ considerably. Since H₂O₂ does not improve the absorbance significantly in the case of Au(III), Cr(VI) or V(V), the addition of H₂O₂ has

been omitted. It has been found that the absorption maxima, intensity and stability of the coloured species depends upon the solvent (dielectric constant) and pH employed. In the case of Fe(III), Cu(II), Ru(III), Ir(III), Mo(VI) or W(VI), peak with maximum absorbance is exhibited in 60% organic solvent media, while in the case of Os(VIII), such behaviour is exhibited in aqueous media. Au(III), Cr(VI) and V(V) exhibit the same maximum absorbance both in aqueous and organic solvent media.

Beer's law limits, optimum photometric range, molar extinction coefficient, relative mean error (%), the relative standard deviation (%) and Sandell's sensitivity of the proposed method in comparison with that of the reported ones are shown in Table 2. A systematic study of the influence of diverse ions has been done and the

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF METAL IONS

Ions μg/25 ml	Fe(III) 0.292 μg	Cu(II) 0.636 μg	Ru(III) 1.35 μg	Mo(VI) 32.6 μg	W(VI) 89.2 μg	Os(VIII) 1.0 μg	Ir(III) 0.31 μg	Au(III) 129.5 μg	Cr(VI) 35.4 μg	V(V) 87.0 μg
NO ₃ ⁻	730	1095	1460	365	1460	1460	780	730	1460	1460
Br ⁻	134	268	672	386	672	672	134	672	672	672
CO ₃ ²⁻	14	57	57	118	11	226	57	566	566	566
B ₄ O ₇ ²⁻	407	203	407	203	407	814	82	407	407	407
Cl ⁻	1214	607	1214	607	1214	1214	303	607	1214	1214
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	Seriously interferes	Seriously interferes	Seriously interferes	Seriously interferes	Seriously interferes	Interferes	Seriously interferes	192	192	192
SO ₄ ²⁻	5.5	110	2.7	27	110	55	11	55	110	110
Citrate	Interferes	Interferes	Seriously interferes	128	64	257	64	643	322	322
Acetate	301	901	1204	301	151	1204	602	602	602	602
EDTA as Na ₂ salt	Interferes	Interferes	Seriously interferes	Interferes	Seriously interferes	Interferes	Seriously interferes	400	400	200
PO ₄ ³⁻	Seriously interferes	32.7	Interferes	164	164	424	164	818	818	818
S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	71	142	71	283	283	Interferes	142	14.2	141	Seriously interferes
Os(VIII)	0.01	0.01	0.18	0.24	0.24	—	0.01	0.05	0.5	0.5
Ru(III)	0.14	0.2	—	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.2	0.34	0.68	0.68
Ir(III)	0.2	0.23	0.77	2.0	2.0	—	—	2.0	2.0	2.0
Au(III)	6.5	13.0	6.5	13.0	5.1	6.5	6.5	—	13.0	6.5
Cr(VI)	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.1	1.8	3.5	3.5	1.8	—	3.0
Pd(II)	2.4	4.8	6.0	12.0	6.0	12.0	2.4	12.0	12.0	12.0
Pt(IV)	23	23	12.0	11.5	11.5	23.0	2.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
Rh(III)	0.21	0.5	1.5	1.0	1.0	2.1	0.5	2.1	1.0	1.0
Fe(III)	—	0.01	0.02	0.23	0.11	0.11	0.01	0.11	0.11	0.11
V(V)	8.7	8.7	8.7	4.3	4.3	8.7	8.7	4.4	2.2	—
Cu(II)	0.025	—	0.05	0.25	0.25	0.5	0.025	0.26	0.18	0.26
K(I)	66	131	328	66	328	328	66	328	328	328
Na(I)	270	405	540	135	540	540	270	270	540	540
Ni(II)	11.5	19.0	7.5	38.0	19.0	38.0	3.8	152	38.0	76
Mo(VI)	2.2	2.2	1.1	—	1.1	2.2	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.55
W(VI)	5.5	5.5	2.8	2.8	—	11.0	2.8	2.2	1.1	2.2
Te(IV)	29	58	5.5	115	58	115	23	58	58	58

TABLE 4—APPLICATION OF THE METHODS TO SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl. No.	Alloy	Composition of the synthetic mixture, ppm	Metal ion	Present ppm	Found by proposed method* ppm
1	Resistac	Cu(II) 0.024 + Al(III) 0.0024 + Fe(III) 0.00025	Cu(II)	0.024	0.0242
2	Manganin	Cu(II) 0.024 + Mn(II) 0.004 + Ni(II) 0.0008	Cu(II)	0.024	0.0243
3	Typewriter metal	Cu(II) 0.024 + Ni(II) 0.008 + Zn(II) 0.008 + Al(III) 0.0012	Cu(II)	0.024	0.0243
4	Cooper's gold	Cu(II) 0.024 + Pt(IV) 0.008 + Zn(II) 0.0008	Cu(II)	0.024	0.0241
5	Phosphor bronze 30	Cu(II) 0.024 + Sn(IV) 0.0012	Cu(II)	0.024	0.0242
6	Coinage bronze	Cu(II) 0.024 + Sn(IV) 0.0012 + Zn(II) 0.00028	Cu(II)	0.024	0.0243
7	Rhotanium	Au(III) 7.2 + Pd(II) 0.8	Au(III)	7.2	7.21
8	Roberts-Austen (purple gold)	Au(III) 5.2 + Al(III) 1.82	Au(III)	5.2	5.202
9	Tungsten filaments	W(VI) 3.98 + Th(IV) 0.02	W(VI)	3.98	3.99
10	Syserkite	Os(VIII) 0.04 + Ir(III) 0.025 + Ru(III) 0.0125 + Pt(IV) 0.01 + Rh(III) 0.0025 + Au(III) 0.0005	Os(VIII)	0.04	0.042
11	Syserkite	Os(VIII) 0.02 + Ir(III) 0.018 + Ru(III) 0.008 + Pt(IV) 0.008 + Rh(III) 0.0002 + Au(III) 0.001	Os(VIII)	0.02	0.021
12	Stainless steel type No. 501	Fe(III) 0.008 + Mn(II) 0.0001 + Cr(VI) 0.0056 + Mo(VI) 0.000032	Fe(III)	0.008	0.0081
13	Tungsten steel	Fe(III) 0.008 + W(VI) 0.0004	Fe(III)	0.008	0.0081
14	Stainless steel type No. 405	Fe(III) 0.008 + Mn(II) 0.000096 + Cr(VI) 0.0011 + Al(III) 0.000028	Fe(III)	0.008	0.0081
15	Steel SAE No. 1095	Fe(III) 0.008 + Mn(II) 0.00004	Fe(III)	0.008	0.008
16	Iridium-platinum alloy	Ir(III) 0.012 + Pt(IV) 0.00064	Ir(III)	0.012	0.012
17	Lab mixture-1	Cr(VI) 2.8 + V(V) 0.08 + Mo(VI) 0.04	Cr(VI)	2.8	2.804
18	Lab mixture-2	Mo(VI) 1.2 + W(VI) 0.06 + Cu(II) 0.004	Mo(VI)	1.2	1.202
19	Lab mixture-3	V(V) 3.5 + Fe(III) 0.004 + Cr(VI) 0.008	V(V)	3.5	3.55
20	Lab mixture-4	Ru(III) 0.08 + Mo(VI) 0.082 + Pd(II) 0.01 + Rh(III) 0.01	Ru(III)	0.08	0.082

* Average of two determinations.

maximum concentrations up to which they do not interfere in the method (within $\pm 4\%$) are mentioned in Table 3. Synthetic mixtures containing the metals corresponding to alloys^{26,27} and a few laboratory mixtures were prepared and the metal ion content in each case was determined. The results are presented in Table 4.

The method is simple and accurate and can be applied for the determinations of very small concentrations of metal ions.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the authorities of the Andhra University, Waltair and U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of Teacher Fellowship to K.V.S.S.M.

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